

Optical Character Recognition Evaluation for Historical Archival Records

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Abstract

The National Archives and Records Administration (NARA) uses an Optical Character Recognition (OCR) model to perform automated transcriptions, but little is known about the performance accuracy of these models on historical documents. This paper evaluates the performance of NARA's OCR model on various document collections and suggests possible areas of improvement to ultimately expand its application with these three research questions: [1] What is the current accuracy, measured by CER and ROUGE, of model transcriptions within various types of documents? [2] What characteristics in a historical document prevent the model from performing well? [3] What options are available for improving performance on document types where performance suffers? This paper offers findings that can strengthen the accuracy and viability of the current OCR model used by NARA, accelerating digitization of historical documents for public researchers. The OCR evaluation strategies explored in this paper can serve as reference material for improvements to the OCR model used by the Archives and other OCR researchers looking to address limitations in model transcription of historical documents.

Key Words: OCR, ROUGE, CER, Federal Statistics, LLMs, NARA

1. Introduction

Optical Character Recognition (OCR) transcription of historical archives has emerged as a critical technology for balancing preservation costs and public accessibility. OCR technology significantly enhances the efficiency of archival digitization by converting scanned documents into editable text. Its fundamental principle involves detecting character contours in images through computer vision algorithms, which are then mapped to machine-encoded text via pattern matching or deep learning models (Amazon Web Services 2025). However, when applied to highly heterogeneous historical archives, the limitations of OCR become apparent. Factors such as faded ink, mixed layouts (handwritten/printed), and non-standardized historical formats lead to significant fluctuations in OCR accuracy.

The National Archives and Records Administration (NARA), as of 2025, manages approximately 13.5 billion pages of textual records, 10 million maps, 40 million photographs, and other formats (U.S. National Archives and Records Administration 2025). Confronted with such vast resources, NARA introduced OCR technology internally in 2019 and publicly in 2024 to assist manual transcription traditionally completed by volunteers (National Archives History Hub 2024). Unfortunately, the performance of its current system varies markedly across document types: accuracy disparities span far and wide, from neatly formatted modern printed reports to faint 19th-century handwritten correspondence. This uncertainty forces archivists into a dilemma—when can OCR be relied upon autonomously, and where should human intervention be

deployed? Therefore, in this paper, we offer solutions based on our statistical and qualitative findings to optimize OCR as a technology in archival sources.

Existing OCR research predominantly focuses on standardized modern printed materials; and among the studies addressing handwritten documents, there is not a direct emphasized focus on archival documents (Memon, Sami, Khan, & Uddin, 2020). Overall, unique challenges posed by archival documents such as degraded ink, hybrid handwritten/printed layouts, and unstructured historical formats are routinely neglected in research. This study addresses this gap by conducting an evaluation of NARA’s operational OCR model on a range of collections that exemplify challenging cases. The dataset encompasses nearly 160 documents spanning the 18th to 21st centuries, comprising 759 data entries categorized as handwritten (~41%), printed (~43%), or mixed (~16%). Recall Oriented Understudy for Gisting Evaluation Longest Common Substring (ROUGE-L) measures the similarity of word sequences, while Character Error Rate (CER) evaluates character-level precision, enabling multi-dimensional error diagnosis. Key findings reveal that OCR achieves superior performance on typed and structured documents but exhibits sharply increased error rates for handwritten materials, specifically pre-1900 samples. Format heterogeneity, rather than document age, emerges as the primary determinant of accuracy. These conclusions challenge conventional assumptions and inform a tiered transcription strategy for NARA: developing human-AI collaborative workflows for mixed-format documents and prioritizing format parsing algorithm optimization. Subsequent sections elaborate on dataset construction and challenges, quantitative analysis, qualitative analysis, and further recommendations of maximizing OCR accuracy.

2. Methodology

2.1 Building the Dataset

The dataset we assembled relies on two key features that enable comparison within all 759 data points: human-annotated text (our ground truth) and OCR-generated transcriptions (coined by NARA as “Extracted Text”). By comparing these two columns, we assessed the OCR model’s strengths and weaknesses. Recognizing the wide variety of document types within NARA’s collections, we also considered the diversity in document formats when analyzing the model’s performance. We recorded key distinctions to categorize our documents: the name of the collection they came from; the page number, when applicable; any externalities present in the document; the access link; the text type (handwritten, typed, or mixed); and the year the document was originally created.

Occasionally, documents would have primarily one type of text (typed or handwritten) and minimal words of the opposite type. In these cases, we classified the documents into the primary type and took note of the other type’s small existence in the externality column. When documents had a more equivalent proportion of typed and handwritten text, they were classified as mixed. While creating our dataset, we found a lack of written documents post 1940s and a lack of typed documents pre 1900s. To mitigate that issue we deployed a word matching strategy, similar to Martínek, Lenc, and Král’s technique, that allowed us to capture a pure typed or handwritten text sample by connecting unique words (2020). The data set example in table 1 shows the full formatting.

Table 1: Sample of rows from our data set, each row represents one transcription and reference text and the respective data attributes

Document Name	Page	Human Annotation	Extracted Text	Externalities (e.g. ripped paper, damage, leave blank if no)	link	type	year
Attorney General's Papers, Office of Office, 1860-1868	30	[handwritten] Mr. Coffey Oath of office Aug. 21, 1861	with simple him tradback & jadi and 110 and tradition product Hous C for 8 sul 1 dosition 85 Twe esall J bno S	The item does have Optical Character Recognition (OCR), but the confidence level is low due to handwriting legibility, typeface clarity or image clarity. Please consider transcribing this page.		handwritten	1861
Cram: Cram, Sarah THR 1		C Sarah Cream Nurse, Co., Regt Appears on Hospital Muster Roll of Trinity Church U.S.A. General Hospital at Georgetown, D. C. for Sept and Oct, 1862. Attached to hospital. When Sept 24, 1862 How employed Nurse Last paid by Maj to, 186. Bounty paid \$ _____ due \$ _____ Present or absent Present Remarks: Book mark: Crosby (343) Copyist	I Saraha beam Nurse, Co., Regt Appears on Hospital Muster Roll of Trinity Church U.S. A. General Hospital, at Georgetown, D. C. for Sept and Oct, 1862. Attached to hospital. When How employed Nurse Sept- 24, 186% Last paid by Maj to, 186. Bounty paid \$ 100, due \$ 100 Present or absent Present Remarks: Book mark: (843) Cameley Copyist		https://catalog.archives.gov/d/75	Mixed	1861
Cram: Cram, Sarah THR 2		Feb 26 1894 32070736	99L OLOZE	Many pages from this collection a	https://catalog.archives.gov/d/75	Mixed	1861
Cram: Cram, Sarah THR 3		C Ann Cramer, Co., Regt Appears on Hospital Muster Roll of Central Park U. S. A. General Hospital, at New York City, N. Y., for to Dec 31, 1862 Attached to hospital When Oct 14 1862, How employed Cooks Last paid by Maj to 186. Bounty paid \$1100, due \$ 1100 Present or absent Present Remarks: Pay due from Oct 14 1862 Book mark: Nebatez (843) Copyist	I Ann Cramer, Co., Regt A ppears on Hospital Muster Roll of Central Park U. S. A. General Hospital, at New York City, N. Y., for to Dec 31, 1862 Attached to hospital When Oct 14 1862, How employed books Last paid by Maj to 186. Bounty paid \$ 100, due \$ 100 Present or absent Present Remarks: Pay due from Oct 14 1862 Book mark: Nebatez (843) Copyist.		https://catalog.archives.gov/d/75	Mixed	1861
Cram: Cram, Sarah THR 4		[red ink] 1884 [vertical] 33040589 [upside down] MAR 26 [vertical]	88907022		https://catalog.archives.gov/d/75	Mixed	1861

Another method we found necessary to eliminate potential confounding biases was to have a vast number of topics covered. Our document collections are different in both their layouts and their content. We collected Civil War documents that showcase a format that features both types of text, typed submarine patrol reports, handwritten oath papers, and other miscellaneous single or collection documents that reflect differences in inherent document traits. Moreover, we observed collections of the same format and content that we looked at throughout 50 years to see if the model performed differently on separate time periods (e.g., Palestinian Jafa Letters from 1872-1915).

A majority of documents within the NARA database have either a human annotation or extracted text, rarely both. This, paired without the existence of a workable API, limited our ability to build a large dataset or scrape for the information, as there is no way to filter based on documents that have human annotations and extracted text. The technique for finding documents was to look at the Citizens Archivist Missions page, a page that holds a collection of documents NARA puts as a top priority for their volunteers. These documents were much more frequently transcribed than those found by random search, most likely because of the attention they receive.

2.2 Data Cleaning

The different approaches transcribers took in their transcriptions proved to be an issue in our initial analysis. Some transcribers would add marks that help a human reader, but that an OCR model would not be reasonably expected to do. The most common occurrence of this was when a document was of mixed type, and the transcriber would write '[handwritten]' to denote that the following words were handwritten. The OCR model was not trained to take that action, so comparing its transcription to a truth value that does so would unfairly decrease the accuracy. There were a multitude of phrases within those square brackets that are not direct references to the transcription (example depicted in figure 1). Our solution was to filter out any phrase within the human annotation column using those square brackets and the text inside. This method is prone to deleting some of the true text from the transcription, but the trade-off between true text and noise text was weighted, and we decided to get rid of any bracket content in the human annotation.

<p>[handwritten]</p> <p>District of Columbia, Washington County } Ss. I, Titian J Coffey Assistant Attorney General of the Attorney General of the United States, do solemnly swear that I will support protect and defend the Constitution of the United States and that I will bear true faith and loyalty to the Government of the United States as established by the Constitution and the laws. [at right] J A Rowland.</p> <p>Sworn & subscribed before me a Justice of the Peace in & for the County of Washington this 20th day of April A. D. 1861. }</p> <p>[at right] T. J. Coffey</p> <p>[at left] Jno. H. Johnson, JP. [written in circle with loops at right of signature] Seal</p>	<p>Districtort@Gmail.com Gimily for ICL, jetian I Coffey spoints Morry Generally the anited states, do dolemnly I wear mas &wide support/pustactive defend the Constitution of the UniverStates and that I with bear true gaith and onality to the governments the hundrestates as established by the Constitution and the laws Swom of subsinal before me Gastic a the Peace midfacting I.Goffey County washing tour this 20'day of April M.D. 1861. Po, 8 Real EQD</p>
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Figure 1: Annotated Sample Entry from Civil War Correspondence Collection, the human transcription on the left contains annotations in square brackets

Similarly, on form documents, the OCR model often misinterprets lines meant for input as underscores, a formatting choice intuitive to humans but not recognized by the model. The manner of cleaning this formatting was to delete any consecutive underscores of length 2 or longer in only the human annotation column. This ensured that all underscores that represented lines were deleted, but not any singular underscores that had meaning. The characters ‘*’ and ‘-’ occasionally were used to represent a page break so we followed the same methodology developed in the underscore cleaning process.

Primary Location of Additional Data:

X State Historic Preservation Office

Other State agency

Federal agency

Local government

University

Other

Name of repository: _____

Figure 2: A transcribed version of a form, in which the transcriber took creative liberty by including simulated markings from the document—namely, underscores to represent write-in lines

The OCR model continuously put phrases on newlines that weren’t attributable to any of the actual text structure. The mechanism we adopted was to scrape both texts of all newline characters and replace them with spaces. This method was the most effective because both documents were reduced to essentially a ‘paragraph formatted text’ to the human eye. But to the computer, it was more digestible.

Finally, to combat capitalization discrepancies, all words within the data set’s human annotation and extracted text column were set to lowercase. This uniformization allowed a stronger focus on the questions at hand.

2.3 Data Disclaimer

While cleaning the data, we encountered several issues both in the source transcriptions and the OCR output. Transcribers occasionally inserted handwritten text within square brackets inconsistently, and though we corrected many of these cases, some likely remain. The cleaning process also inadvertently removed a small amount of valid text, and the OCR model introduced

quirks such as unnecessary line breaks unrelated to the document's actual structure. Additionally, our dataset was limited in size due to the availability of documents containing both human annotations and extracted text. Despite these limitations, the adjustments we made ensured the transcriptions were accurate enough for meaningful analysis, with the benefits of cleaning far outweighing the minimal loss of original text.

2.4 Quantitative Analysis Methods

Our quantitative analysis serves as a way to mathematically evaluate the performance of the OCR model with historically used text comparison metrics. By creating scores, we can algorithmically differentiate documents within their groups. Two evaluation metrics were used for quantitative comparison: Recall-Oriented Understudy for Gisting Evaluation (ROUGE) and Character Error Rate (CER). Both metrics calculate accuracy scores by comparing generated text to a reference text, which, in this case, compares NARA's OCR output to the human annotation. There are a few different common ROUGE metrics, we used ROUGE-L because it rewards correct in-order word sequences without requiring exact adjacency, making it well-suited for evaluating OCR output. As its name suggests, CER differs from ROUGE metrics in that it evaluates the accuracy of individual characters between the generated and reference texts, meaning that it is a much stricter metric. We selected these two lexical text similarity metrics based on Goma and Fahmy's work because they offer a balanced approach using string-based methods that closely reflect how humans judge translation quality (2013).

The main objective of this analysis was to determine which characteristics of a certain text led to better performance of the OCR model. There were two characteristics that we focused on in our analysis: the type of document (i.e., was the original text handwritten, typed, or a mix of the two) and the year that the document was created. From what we had researched about OCR models, we expected to see much better performance in all metrics for the typed documents than the handwritten documents, simply due to the consistent formatting and uniform letters. To test this, we examined the differences in accuracy (using ROUGE and CER metrics) across all the documents in the dataset, which consisted of 759 documents (328 typed, 312 handwritten, and 119 mixed). We did this by using a two-sample t-test to compare the mean scores within each metric.

We collected more documents from a series of collections of documents that covered a large time span, to determine if document age influenced OCR model performance. The series, "United States Consular Records for Jaffa, Palestine, 1872–1917" covers a time span of 45 years, and there is a mix of both written and typed documents. We collected the human annotations and transcriptions of 176 documents (108 handwritten and 68 typed). By looking at accuracy metrics over the years and between types of documents, we would be able to tell what effect, if any, the year of the document has on the accuracy of the transcription while controlling for document type. We looked at the correlation coefficient and the F-statistic of that coefficient to establish a relationship between age and performance.

2.5 Qualitative Analysis Methods

While quantitative analysis allows us to assess document type and age as performance predictors, qualitative analysis allows us to isolate traits that aren't as easily measurable for assessment. Our qualitative analysis of documents relied on our previous calculations to address which documents should be prioritized for an in-depth look. We looked at the two scores we calculated to conduct our quantitative analysis, CER and ROUGE-L Recall to rank documents from worst performing to best. ROUGE scores range from 0 to 1, where 1 is the best, a score can be. Whereas CER scores generally range from 0 to 1, where 0 is the best, a score can be. However, CER scores can exceed 1 in the scenario where the text being measured is longer than the source text (e.g. truth value of 'abc' transcription of '123123' has CER of 2). In our calculations we only found 8 documents with $CER > 1$, so we did not normalize our data and took careful note of these instances. Understanding ROUGE and CER scores were inverse signs of strength; we used the formula: Ensemble Score = $-(1 - ROUGE) + CER$. The ensemble score afforded us an easy ranking

system, and scores were inverted to create consistency within analysis. With the Ensemble Score formula, we sorted the documents and looked in depth at the top 30 scoring and lowest 30 scoring documents. We then took note of any and all characteristics that existed in the 60 identified documents to compare traits to theorize as the reasoning behind the scores. Figure 3 below shows what an average observation contains.

Attorney General's Papers: Oaths of Office, 1860-1868 Pg 38

The text on the other side of the image is extremely visible as it bleeds through. It seems the OCR model is picking up on this text because the reference text is only a few words but the extracted text is at least 10x the length. Because CER can exceed 1, the score captured is abnormally high due to the amount of words that are 'picked up' over the reference amount. There is also a rip on the page. It seems to be out of the way of the text.

Figure 3: Qualitative observation of traits in document make that could theoretically confound or improve model behavior from page 38 of “Attorney General’s Papers: Oaths of Office” collection

3. Results

Section 3.1 presents a quantitative analysis of OCR performance, first comparing accuracy across document types using ROUGE-L and CER scores and statistical testing, then evaluating how document age affects accuracy using linear regression models with and without interaction terms. Section 3.2 complements this with a qualitative analysis of the best and worst performing documents, identifying specific layout, damage, and formatting traits that influenced OCR results and highlighting instances of unusual model behavior. Section 3.3 touches on the limitations of the dataset.

3.1 Quantitative Analysis

3.1.1 Influence of Document Type on OCR Performance

Figure 4: Boxplot of ROUGE-L Scores by Document Type

Figure 4 shows the distribution of the recall, precision, and F1 scores by document type. Recall was the highest, on average, for typed documents, which had a mean recall of 0.897 and a median recall of 0.938. Mixed documents perform slightly worse, with a mean of 0.730 and a median of 0.744. Handwritten documents received the lowest scores for all metrics out of all three document types, with a mean and median recall of 0.598 and 0.625, respectively. Handwritten documents

have the largest variation in all scores, with a standard deviation of 0.203 (as compared to typed and mixed respective .140 and .109).

Two-sample t-tests were run between types to determine whether there was a difference in means of ROUGE-L recall scores. We found that there is very strong evidence to suggest that there is a difference in the means between each group, with all p-values far below 0.01. (See appendix table 5a.)

Following the same framework, we looked at the differences in CER between document types.

Figure 5: Boxplot of CER Scores by Document Type

We see that typed documents have a lower CER, with a mean and median of 0.107 and 0.033, respectively. This means that the average typed document wrongly translated 10.7% of characters, and half wrongly translated 3.3% of characters. On the other hand, the mean and median for mixed documents are 0.285 and 0.220, respectively, and 0.479 and 0.295, respectively, for handwritten documents. This means that in our sample, the average handwritten document had more errors than correct translations. The graph excludes five outliers from the handwritten group—two with CER scores above 17—likely caused by model hallucination, which skews the data right and inflates the mean relative to the median, especially since CER can exceed one.

Again, to prove that there is a difference in the mean CER between these groups, we ran two-sample t-tests. We found that there was extremely strong evidence to suggest that there is a difference in means between typed and handwritten documents, as well as typed and mixed documents ($p < .001$). And while there was evidence to suggest that there is a difference in means between handwritten and mixed documents, the p-value was much greater ($.01 < p < .05$). (See appendix table 5b.)

From the t-tests conducted on both ROUGE and CER, it is reasonable to conclude that there is a statistical difference in the accuracy of transcriptions between handwritten, typed, and mixed documents.

3.1.2 Influence of Age on OCR Performance

To determine whether document age played a significant role in accuracy, we examined 176 documents (108 handwritten and 68 typed) from a single series of collections and created corresponding linear regression models to see the magnitude of the effect of year on accuracy.

Figure 6: Relationship between ROUGE-L Recall and Year in Palestinian Letter Collection

Figure 6 represents all the documents in the series, and the regression line for a linear model with year as the sole predictor. The model has an R^2 value of 0.003, meaning the year of the document alone explains 0.3% of the variation in ROUGE-L recall scores in this sample. With a p-value of 0.441, it is safe to say that there is no evidence that the ROUGE-L recall scores change over time. Next, we looked at CER using the same methods. (See appendix figure 13a.)

Figure 7: Relationship between CER and Year in Palestinian Letter Collection

In the test illustrated by figure 7, year was an even worse predictor of CER than recall. With an R^2 value below 0.001 and a p-value of 0.991, we conclude that year is not a good predictor of either metric that we are using to determine accuracy. (See appendix figure 13b.) The next test will add a categorical variable with an interaction to the models, using document type.

Figure 8: Relationship between ROUGE-L Recall and Year by Document Type in Palestinian Letter Collection

Figure 8 shows the relationship between year and recall, while considering document type. There is a clear difference between the two groups, with typed having a higher recall score, on average. This model performed much better than the previous model, with an R^2 value of 0.59. It shows that typed documents tend to have higher recall scores than handwritten ones. In this sample of data, typed scores decreased slightly over time, but handwritten documents showed little change. Once again, with a p-value of 0.441, year on its own is not a meaningful predictor of recall. However, with a p-value of 0.054, there is some evidence to suggest that the interaction between year and type is significant (i.e., the effect of year may be different between types). (See appendix figure 13c.)

Figure 9: Relationship between CER and Year by Document Type in Palestinian Letter Collection

Figure 9 shows a similar linear model, but with CER as the response variable. This model had an R^2 value of 0.387, and similar to the previous model, it is still statistically significant overall with a p-value of the F-statistic below 0.001 (this means that at least one variable adds explanatory value to the model). Again, the year is not a significant predictor of CER, and typed documents have lower CER's than handwritten documents. There is also some evidence that CER increases over time for typed documents. (See appendix figure 13d.)

All of these results point to a few major takeaways: there is a significant statistical difference in the accuracy of different document types, year cannot be used as a meaningful predictor of accuracy metrics, and there must be other possible variables, which we did not test for, that

contribute to the accuracy of a transcription. The last point becomes more obvious once we look at why CER increases and ROUGE-L recall decreases for typed documents over time.

Typed document, c. 1889

Typed document, c. 1898

Figure 10: A Document Created with Typesetting Compared to a Document Created with a Typewriter

The documents pictured in figure 10 show two different typed documents from 1889 (left) and 1898 (right). The document on the left was likely created using typesetting and distributed widely. Documents like this are the only instance of typed documents before the 1890s that we came across during our data collection. The document on the right was likely created using a typewriter, and there are a lot of marks, strikethroughs, and corrections on the page. While typed documents became more common in the late 1800s due to the rise in the adoption of typewriters, this also led to a decrease in quality, as mistakes had to be fixed after the fact. This could be a reason why the linear models estimated decreases in accuracy over time in typed documents.

3.2 Qualitative Analysis

The scores we derived in our quantitative analyses tell us type, but not age, can determine when a document will be accurately transcribed or not. However, without looking at the content of the documents and trying to understand the OCR output compared to the text on the document, a full understanding of performance determinants cannot be achieved. The ensemble scores we created, that properly weigh CER and ROUGE, presented us with the ability to isolate the 30 worst performing documents and 30 best performing documents.

3.2.1 Lowest Scoring Documents

The documents with lower transcription performance initially appeared random. The majority were handwritten and the documents varied in size, aging, length, and general formatting. Documents with higher CER scores (CER > 1) were examined first; they often showed distortions

that, upon closer analysis of traits and model behavior, helped us make more informed assumptions

Table 2: Ten worst performing documents in ascending order. Document Name, Page, Year, Type, ROUGE-L-r score, CER, and Ensemble score all shown

	Document Name	Page	year	type	ROUGE-l-r	CER	Ensemble Score
1	Attorney General's Papers: Oaths of Office, 18...	36.0	1865	Handwritten	0.000000	19.545455	-20.545455
2	Attorney General's Papers: Oaths of Office, 18...	38.0	1865	Handwritten	0.000000	17.818182	-18.818182
3	Attorney General's Papers: Oaths of Office, 18...	32.0	1866	Handwritten	0.071429	7.692308	-8.620879
4	Attorney General's Papers: Oaths of Office, 18...	30.0	1861	Handwritten	0.000000	2.473684	-3.473684
5	Activity Number Index 1970	1.0	1970	Handwritten	0.000000	1.272727	-2.272727
6	Voting Rights Act (2)	17.0	1981	Typed	0.014440	0.979397	-1.964957
7	Activity Number Index 1959	1.0	1959	Handwritten	0.000000	0.950000	-1.950000
8	Cram: Cram, Sarah THRU Cravin, Mahala	2.0	1861	Typed	0.000000	0.950000	-1.950000
9	Attorney General's Papers: Oaths of Office, 18...	14.0	1861	Handwritten	0.000000	0.947368	-1.947368
10	Activity Number Index 1949-1950	1.0	1950	Handwritten	0.000000	0.923077	-1.923077

CER scores as high as 19.5 existed in our dataset, which is not anything to be ignored. The four lowest scoring documents were all from the ‘Attorney General's Papers: Oaths of Office, 1860-1868’ collection and had CER’s greater than 1. We noted that by the nature of CER being greater than 1, it meant more is being transcribed than present on the document in all observed CER > 1 instances. This interpretation of OCR scores as a result of model actions, led to us discovering a key weakness in the OCR model. All four of these documents had fold impressions and small rips but that wasn’t where the disproportionate CER’s were coming from as neither overlapped with the text. The text on the other side of each document was extremely visible and bleeding through, to a hue a few shades lighter than the text on the front side. Therefore, it was clear the OCR model picked up and attempted to transcribe these mirrored characters resulting in the high CER score. Notably, the model’s choice to read this as text wouldn’t have even been considered by a human transcriber, signaling a defining difference between an automated transcription and a human one.

The documents that followed the lowest four scoring documents revealed more traits that weren’t necessarily intuitive as indicators of success because to a human they are subconsciously ignored. Several documents showed high CER and high ROUGE scores, this contradiction meant a majority of the phrases in the reference text were present in the translated text, but in a completely wrong order. Documents that did score high in both were documents that were segmented in a way that disrupts a left to right reading pattern. Take a newspaper for example, there are columns that we as humans are taught to read top to bottom column-wise then left to right. The OCR model proved it couldn’t segregate text based on clear spacing in any document that was supposed to be read in a non-exclusive left to right manner. From documents of two columned numbered lists to newspapers, to documents with random notes and placement of text blocks, and to any document with text that didn’t exist on the same linear axis the model scored high in both score categories. Format didn’t play exactly the role we thought it would in our analysis, not all atypical formats are transcribed improperly. Exclusively, formats that introduce text layouts that aren’t homogeneous to left and right reading style perform poorly. The OCR model’s inability to discriminate between clearly separated segmentation highlights another key weakness that human transcribers don’t exhibit.

On the other hand, there were traits that continuously stumped human transcribers and the OCR model. Faded text, cursive handwriting, aggressive aging, water damage, impression lines, unique

handwriting styles, and other traits of the sorts caused poor OCR transcription and human error (e.g. “[illegible]” in transcription) when it overlapped the text. Originally, we assumed most of these traits would come inherently with age, hence our year compared to scores analysis. And while older documents more consistently contained one or more of the traits that directly impacted text legibility, it was still a prevalent issue among all years. Additionally, old documents performed very well in both ROUGE and CER so long as they were preserved properly.

3.2.2 Highest Scoring Documents

In a trend that follows our quantitative analysis we found that the best thirty performing documents were exclusively typed, apart from one perfect scoring handwritten document. Documents that were able to score high on ROUGE and low on CER exhibited more consistent defining traits than that of their counterpart.

Table 3: Ten best documents in descending order. Document Name, Page, Year, Type, ROUGE-L-r score, CER, and Ensemble score all shown

	Document Name	Page	year	type	ROUGE-l-r	CER	Ensemble Score
1	Oswald, Lee Harvey - Pre-Russian Period - 3-Ed...	1.0	1964	Handwritten	1.000000	0.000000	0.000000
2	[Palestine - Jaffa - Consulate] Official and M...	110.0	1887	Typed	1.000000	0.000000	0.000000
3	Voting Rights Act (2)	4.0	1981	Typed	1.000000	0.000000	0.000000
4	November 21, 1892 Red Lake	6.0	1892	Typed	1.000000	0.000000	0.000000
5	[Palestine - Jaffa - Consulate] Official and M...	126.0	1888	Typed	1.000000	0.000643	-0.000643
6	Report on the Role of the Volunteer Family Sup...	3.0	1981	Typed	1.000000	0.002460	-0.002460
7	[Palestine - Jaffa - Consulate] Official and M...	229.0	1889	Typed	1.000000	0.005291	-0.005291
8	Voting Rights Act (2)	9.0	1981	Typed	1.000000	0.005917	-0.005917
9	Voting Rights Act (2)	3.0	1981	Typed	1.000000	0.006729	-0.006729
10	[Palestine - Jaffa - Consulate] Official and M...	264.0	1893	Typed	0.995392	0.003220	-0.007828

The singular perfect score handwritten document was a very small sample of text, only three lines in length. It was parsed using the matching technique mentioned in the methods section. The text contains letters, numbers, and special characters in print handwriting. Oddly enough, the text is on the tab of a folder which is not a traditional text presentation but still was observed correctly by the model.

The typed documents that scored perfectly varied in length of the actual text contained in the document. This was found to be a common pattern among all scoring levels of documents, the amount of text was not as big of a factor in OCR model accuracy as we would’ve conjectured, though in some instances it can make a difference, like the perfect scored handwritten sample. Another inconsistency among the top typed documents was the actual format of the documents. One was a letter with differing indentation, one was a typed paragraph, and the other was an excerpt-like body of text that was rotated 45 degrees. The perfect scores in these differing compositions support our findings in the high scoring documents. Document format doesn’t impact OCR’s abilities if the text is intended to be read strictly left to right. Even when rotated text is present, the model handles it with ease because it follows conventional text patterns. Lastly, these documents all were clearly legible, and any signs of aging did not overlap with the text whatsoever.

The remaining high scoring documents were more of the same: standard typed documents and signs of aging were off to the side. There were some unique features in top documents including multiple fonts in one document, certain fonts being bolder than the rest within the same text, and heavily numeric content. All these attributes did not have an impact on transcription which narrowed down the list of potential OCR confounders.

Finally, the document “[Palestine - Jaffa - Consulate] Official and Miscellaneous Letters Pg. 264” and other letters in the collection had two stamp-esque sections embedded in the text (see figure 11). The original transcriber wrote down the text left to right instead of top to bottom left to right, despite obvious spacing. When looking at the OCR transcription, the model acted identically. Thus, justifying our claim, the model only reads left to right. Had the transcriber properly segmented this text, the CER score would’ve been higher and it’s unlikely this document would’ve been in the best thirty.

Figure 11: [Palestine - Jaffa - Consulate] Official and Miscellaneous Letters Pg. 264 text that was transcribed as “1893. TREASURY DEPARTMENT, ...” instead of “1893. Department No. 14.”

3.2.3 Defective Model Behavior

Our findings from looking at the top and bottom 30 documents were undeniably decisive. Documents that scored a certain way always have explanations as to why, and the previously mentioned behaviors were more easily distinguishable. Interestingly though, in our analysis we had some confusing transcriptions that had issues we didn’t even theorize would come about. There were four instances among our lowest scoring documents where the OCR was actually reading the text upside down. This conclusion took a while to understand and visualize, but once we did, we saw more instances. Text bodies that were shorter in nature and had unique backgrounds were inconsistently being transcribed upside down.

Table 4: Original transcription, rotated transcription (180 degrees), original text image, and truth value of text shown in line to highlight the OCR model mistakenly transcribing text upside down

Original Transcription	Rotated Transcription	Text Image	Truth Value
OS + bt X30NI	IN03X 1q + SO	INDEX 49 + 50	INDEX 49 & 50
6967- 8967 X3CN T	1 NC3X 7967-8967		PERS-N311 Microfilm Index 1968 - 1969
ten VOLUDAY W 41 \$ expire eibl	eibl W 41 \$ expire VOLUDAY ten		1970 MICROFILM LOCATOR
3NO a	e ONE		ONE

Our sample size included numerous examples where the original content looked similar to the incorrectly axised content in table 4. However, the model didn't always act incorrectly, which makes it unclear when and how it chooses to do so. It is likely the background and placement of the text were the determining causes, but we are unable to come to a solid conclusion.

4. Recommendations to Improve OCR Accuracy

Our results can provide important insight into how NARA, and any other large archival source, should move forward with using OCR technology. Comparing across types of documents and years allows us to determine which documents are most effectively transcribed by OCR and which documents human volunteers should place more focus on when transcribing. Typed documents tended to show very high recall, precision, and F1 scores and low CER scores in comparison to handwritten documents, which suggests that human transcribers can rely more heavily on OCR transcriptions when creating their own human transcription. It is already a common practice for NARA volunteers to start with the OCR transcription and edit it to 100% accuracy. We suggest more emphasis should be placed on utilizing OCR transcriptions, especially in typed documents, to minimize transcription time consumed on individual documents. However, our findings suggest this method isn't possible for all documents, with handwritten documents having the least viable OCR transcriptions. Documents where that is the case will need the most amount of human attention. Those documents will benefit the least from the help of OCR and should follow traditional manual transcription practices to remain time effective.

Qualitative analysis of the documents OCR failed to convey insights that stress the differences between human transcriptions and automated ones. With these findings, we introduce novel techniques to improve OCR accuracy. We want to extend the scope of how the OCR model and human transcribers work together. The documents with the worst transcriptions often were not due just to aging and/or atypical handwriting. Documents with trends of irregular segmentation, different text alignment, or bleeding through text caused the most confusion to the model. With this in mind, we suggest human efforts start with a choice of 'boxing' around text. If a transcriber gets to a document and believes the model would be able to produce an accurate transcription faster via boxing, they can choose to box the document instead. By boxing, the OCR model errors caused by its own programmatic faults will significantly decrease. For example, text that bled through won't be in the area the model transcribes, text with multiple rotations will not be perceived as a whole, etc.

Figure 12: Boxing demonstration on the “Great Lakes Bulletin”, boxes are around segmented parts of the text and numbered

A document could possess multiple boxes and the text within each box would then be ordered corresponding to box order, as shown in figure 12. Additionally, the rotation of the text would be determined by the corner where the volunteer starts the box, the starting corner would be considered the top side of the text. Both intuitive features built into the boxing methodology would ensure that OCR errors would significantly decrease, simply by erasing confusion.

5. Conclusion

To summarize our findings, our analysis demonstrated the highest CER and ROUGE scores and therefore, higher accuracy among typed documents. Handwritten documents tended to show the widest range of scores. Mixed-type documents showed notably higher performance than fully handwritten documents, but lower than typed. Additionally, the OCR model tended to struggle more with documents that showed greater irregularity. Documents with abnormal formats, ink bled through from other pages, or complex handwriting consistently showed low accuracy scores. The make of a document is not something that can be changed or controlled in any archival collection. Factors like wear and tear, age, typeface, among a few, are inevitable challenges transcribers will always have to overcome. By using OCR technology in combination with human volunteers, more documents can be accurately transcribed and increase public access to information. Our proposed solution allows a feasible way to combine machine power with human power to do just that.

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Appendix

We used the ROUGE-L metric from the `rouge-score` Python package to evaluate overall similarity between OCR-generated text and human reference transcriptions. ROUGE-L Recall specifically measures how much of the reference text is successfully captured by the OCR output, prioritizing longest common subsequences.

CER was calculated using the `cer` function from the `jiwer` Python package. CER measures the number of character-level insertions, deletions, and substitutions required to transform OCR output into the reference transcription, normalized by the number of characters in the reference.

To evaluate differences in ROUGE-L and CER between document types, we conducted two-sample t-tests assuming unequal variances using `scipy.stats.ttest_ind`. For example, to test ROUGE-L recall differences between typed and handwritten documents:

Table 5a: ROUGE-L Recall t-test between different document types

Comparison	t-statistic	p-value
Typed vs Handwritten	21.607491776050857	2.086077133717593e-75
Typed vs Mixed	13.222522347549125	4.5964824572825305e-31
Handwritten vs Mixed	-8.710702654701153	9.166828759080597e-17

Table 5b: CER t-test between different document types

Comparison	t-statistic	p-value
Typed vs Handwritten	-4.226037840976577	3.104595575060554e-05
Typed vs Mixed	-8.359437442549861	9.330326355921737e-15
Handwritten vs Mixed	2.176253110592767	0.030230035693311723

Results showed highly statistically significant differences ($p < 0.001$) in most comparisons between document types for both ROUGE-L and CER, except between mixed and handwritten documents for CER, which still has had statistically significant differences [not highly] ($p < 0.05$).

Ordinary Least Squares Regression (OLS)

To assess whether document year was a significant predictor of OCR accuracy, we fit OLS regression models using `statsmodels.formula.api`. The dependent variables were ROUGE-L recall and CER, and independent variables included year, document type, and an interaction term.

Key findings:

- Year alone was not a significant predictor ($p > 0.4$ for ROUGE, $p > 0.99$ for CER).
- Including document type improved model fit significantly.
- Interaction between year and type had marginal significance ($p \approx 0.054$).
- R^2 values: ~ 0.59 for ROUGE model, ~ 0.39 for CER model.

```

=====
                        OLS Regression Results
=====
Dep. Variable:          Q("ROUGE-l-r")    R-squared:                0.003
Model:                  OLS                Adj. R-squared:           -0.002
Method:                 Least Squares      F-statistic:              0.5971
Date:                   Thu, 17 Apr 2025   Prob (F-statistic):       0.441
Time:                   18:12:31          Log-Likelihood:           61.596
No. Observations:      183                AIC:                      -119.2
Df Residuals:           181                BIC:                      -112.8
Df Model:                1
Covariance Type:        nonrobust
=====

```

	coef	std err	t	P> t	[0.025	0.975]
Intercept	2.3813	2.049	1.162	0.247	-1.662	6.424
year	-0.0008	0.001	-0.773	0.441	-0.003	0.001

```

=====
Omnibus:                 38.991    Durbin-Watson:            0.602
Prob(Omnibus):           0.000    Jarque-Bera (JB):         65.051
Skew:                    -1.095    Prob(JB):                  7.49e-15
Kurtosis:                 4.932    Cond. No.:                 3.02e+05
=====

```

Figure 13a: Predicting ROUGE-L Recall with Year

```

=====
                        OLS Regression Results
=====
Dep. Variable:          Q("CER")          R-squared:                0.000
Model:                  OLS                Adj. R-squared:           -0.006
Method:                 Least Squares      F-statistic:              0.0001278
Date:                   Thu, 17 Apr 2025   Prob (F-statistic):       0.991
Time:                   18:26:21          Log-Likelihood:           58.807
No. Observations:      183                AIC:                      -113.6
Df Residuals:           181                BIC:                      -107.2
Df Model:                1
Covariance Type:        nonrobust
=====

```

	coef	std err	t	P> t	[0.025	0.975]
Intercept	0.2057	2.080	0.099	0.921	-3.899	4.311
year	-1.242e-05	0.001	-0.011	0.991	-0.002	0.002

```

=====
Omnibus:                 27.526    Durbin-Watson:            0.902
Prob(Omnibus):           0.000    Jarque-Bera (JB):         35.253
Skew:                    1.059    Prob(JB):                  2.21e-08
Kurtosis:                 3.370    Cond. No.:                 3.02e+05
=====

```

Figure 13b: Predicting CER with Year

```

=====
                        OLS Regression Results
=====
Dep. Variable:          Q("ROUGE-L-r")    R-squared:                0.587
Model:                 OLS                Adj. R-squared:           0.580
Method:               Least Squares       F-statistic:              84.82
Date:                 Thu, 17 Apr 2025    Prob (F-statistic):      3.46e-34
Time:                 18:10:10           Log-Likelihood:          142.22
No. Observations:     183                AIC:                     -276.4
Df Residuals:         179                BIC:                     -263.6
Df Model:              3
Covariance Type:      nonrobust
=====
                        coef    std err          t      P>|t|    [0.025    0.975]
-----
Intercept             -0.8431     1.708     -0.494    0.622    -4.213     2.527
type[T.Typed]         5.5418     2.715     2.041    0.043     0.183    10.900
year                   0.0008     0.001     0.897    0.371    -0.001     0.003
year:type[T.Typed]   -0.0028     0.001    -1.942    0.054    -0.006    4.43e-05
=====
Omnibus:              93.135    Durbin-Watson:            1.472
Prob(Omnibus):        0.000    Jarque-Bera (JB):        546.792
Skew:                 -1.846    Prob(JB):                1.84e-119
Kurtosis:             10.621    Cond. No.                 7.44e+05
=====

```

Figure 13c: Predicting ROUGE-L Recall with Year and Type

```

=====
                        OLS Regression Results
=====
Dep. Variable:          Q("CER")          R-squared:                0.387
Model:                 OLS                Adj. R-squared:           0.377
Method:               Least Squares       F-statistic:              37.65
Date:                 Thu, 17 Apr 2025    Prob (F-statistic):      6.51e-19
Time:                 19:08:16           Log-Likelihood:          103.57
No. Observations:     183                AIC:                     -199.1
Df Residuals:         179                BIC:                     -186.3
Df Model:              3
Covariance Type:      nonrobust
=====
                        coef    std err          t      P>|t|    [0.025    0.975]
-----
Intercept             3.4618     2.110     1.641    0.103    -0.701     7.625
type[T.Typed]        -6.0919     3.354    -1.816    0.071    -12.711     0.527
year                  -0.0017     0.001    -1.512    0.132    -0.004     0.001
year:type[T.Typed]   0.0031     0.002     1.751    0.082    -0.000     0.007
=====
Omnibus:              42.116    Durbin-Watson:            1.507
Prob(Omnibus):        0.000    Jarque-Bera (JB):        71.338
Skew:                 1.174    Prob(JB):                3.23e-16
Kurtosis:             4.961    Cond. No.                 7.44e+05
=====

```

Figure 13d: Predicting CER with Year and Type